

Selecting and Isolating Specific LIDAR Classification Groups (e.g., Vegetation, or Buildings) into a Separate GIS Layer

Creating New GIS Layers from LIDAR Dataset Based on ASPRS-Defined Classification Values

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Creating separate GIS layers from a LiDAR dataset allows for tailored visualization. For instance, you can use different color schemes or styles to highlight vegetation in one layer and other features in separate layers.

Isolating the ground class, for example, enables focused analysis of terrain and surface features, which is essential for tasks like topographic mapping and terrain modeling. Separating the buildings class allows for detailed examination of urban structures, crucial for city planning, infrastructure development, and property management.

Overall, isolating different classes into separate GIS layers enhances data management and supports more precise and effective analysis.

SGIS enables these modifications using the 'LIDAR' toolbox.

We previously loaded a point cloud into SGIS v.R. Opening the 'Lidar' toolbox reveals a dialog window where we have already seen how to populate the memo box with existing classification codes, uncheck non-existing classifications, and change colors.

Now, in the 'Tools' tab, locate the 'Selection by Checked Classifications' function. This function selects and highlights all points within the checked classes. If only one classification is checked, only those points will be selected and highlighted. If multiple classifications are checked, such as ground and buildings, points from all selected classifications will be highlighted.

This tool is valuable because it works with the 'Selected Elements in New Layer' function, allowing you to isolate and export these points into separate GIS layers.

Let's walk through the process step by step.

Fig. 19 Use the 'Selection by Checked Classifications' function in the 'Tools' tab to highlight points from selected classifications. This tool facilitates isolating and exporting these points into separate GIS layers.

Fig.20 In the Classifications tab, all classes except for 'Buildings' are unchecked. After clicking 'Apply,' only the Building classification is displayed in the graphics panel.

After importing a LAS file, click on the 'LIDAR' function. In the Tools tab, select 'Get Existing Classifications.' Once they are displayed in the memo box, click 'Uncheck non-existing' to simplify the list. Now, in the Classifications tab, uncheck all but the 'Buildings' class for demonstration purposes. Click 'Apply' to transfer these settings to the graphics panel, where only the Building classification will be visible. If you want to reset or choose a different classification, simply click 'Clear' to remove the current selection.

Fig.21 To reset or select a different classification, click "Clear" to remove the current selection from the graphics panel.

Fig.22 Selecting and highlighting low, medium, and high vegetation classifications using the 'Selection By Checked Classification' function.

You can also select and highlight multiple classifications at once. For example, to select low, medium, and high vegetation classifications, simply check all three boxes and click on 'Selection By Checked Classification'.

Fig.23 Vegetation classifications are instantly selected and highlighted in red within the graphics panel.

All vegetation classifications are instantly selected and highlighted in red within the graphics panel.

To isolate these points into a separate GIS layer, simply click on the 'Selected in New Layer' function.

Fig.24 Vegetation classifications are selected and highlighted in red, ready to be isolated into a separate GIS layer using the 'Selected in New Layer' function.

The function will prompt you to name the new layer. We'll enter 'Vegetation' and then click 'OK' to proceed.

Fig.25 Naming the new layer as 'Vegetation' and clicking 'OK' to complete the process.

The new layer, containing only Low, Medium, and High Vegetation classifications, is immediately created and visible in the Layers panel.

This completes the procedure.

Fig.26 The new layer with Low, Medium, and High Vegetation classifications is created and visible in the Layers panel.